

High Seas Fisheries and Ocean Carbon – Decision Support Tools and Future Scenarios

30th April 2025, 10.00 – 14.00 CET/09.00 – 13.00 GMT

Online Teams Meeting

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OceanICU Website: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>

Stakeholder Sign-Up Sheet: <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUsignup>

OceanICU is co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101083922 (OceanICU) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10054454, 10063673, 10064020, 10059241, 10079684, 10059012, 10048179]. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Suggested citation: Culhane, F., Berzaghi, F., Cariou, T., Gallo, N., Lehodey, P., Mariani, G., Sanders, R., Sontot-Marjary, M. and Bruggeman, J. (2025) High Seas Fisheries and Ocean Carbon – Decision Support Tools and Future Scenarios: Summary Workshop Report. Marine Institute, Ireland. Version 1.0

Executive Summary

The OceanICU project hosted an online stakeholder workshop on the 30th April 2025. This workshop focussed on the high seas fishing community, its interactions with ocean carbon, and getting feedback on the development of future scenarios and the OceanICU Decision Support Tool. It was attended by 12 participants. The workshop had a dedicated half-day to discuss these topics. At the workshop, a series of presentations introduced the OceanICU project; outcomes of previous stakeholder engagements on the topic of ocean carbon; tools (models) being used within the project; the OceanICU Decision Support Tool; and the concept of Ocean System Pathways. Time was provided for open discussion (Q&A) around the topics presented and formal feedback was obtained through using online Mentimeter polls.

Key outcomes of the workshop included:

- Participants stated that to maintain our current supply of food from fish, reinvestment in the fishing industry is required if we also want to reduce the carbon footprint of fisheries (including those resulting from the disturbance of the sediment via bottom trawling). The fishing industry is working towards sustainability but does not have other options to both reduce emissions and maintain food supply.
- Participants feel that it is important for decision makers need to understand the wider context, trade-offs and the consequences of decisions, which are potentially complex and currently unclear. For example,
 - What is the significance of fisheries impacts in terms of total ocean carbon?
 - Any reduction in food supply coming from fish and replaced by other equivalent sources of proteins will have wider implications for carbon but also water use, land use, and other environmental impacts.
 - Displacement of fisheries from areas of high carbon sequestration may have wider impacts if e.g. abundance of fish stocks are lower in displaced areas.
- Identification of participant preferences for how to configure the OceanICU Decision Support Tool (DST).
- Development of future scenarios should consider the current management already in operation.

The discussions and feedback received from the polls will inform the ongoing research trajectories in the OceanICU project. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the participants and wider stakeholder group.

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1. Workshop Goals and Set-Up

1.1 Goals

The OceanICU project focuses on better understanding the interactions and potential effects of fishing on ocean carbon and assessing if those effects are large enough to interfere with ocean carbon uptake and affect climate change, and how a range of tools could be used to answer this question. In this workshop we aimed to get **stakeholder feedback on the development of future scenarios and the OceanICU Decision Support Tool** to guide work going forward in the project and ensure relevance of our work to the needs of the fishing industry and society.

This workshop followed on from the previous “**High Seas Fisheries and Ocean carbon – An interactive online workshop**” workshop held in February 2024. In that workshop, we discussed the links between fishing, ocean carbon and climate change, gathering stakeholder perceptions on the interactions between fishing activity and ocean carbon.

1.2 Intended Outcomes

During the workshop, we:

- Presented outcomes of the previous stakeholder engagement including stakeholder co-developed conceptual models and emergent themes,
- Showcased tools (models) being used within the project, and gathered feedback on them and their use, inputs, and potential future scenarios,
- Described the development of a Decision Support Tool within OceanICU, and gathered opinions and feedback on user needs and potential applications,
- Introduced the concept of Ocean System Pathways for considering future scenarios.

The format of the workshop included a mixture of informative talks and interactive sessions. Through this, the intended outcomes were the identification of relevant management/policy questions and the development of realistic future scenarios to progress towards applied tool development and ensure OceanICU outputs meet stakeholder and end-user needs. We intend to build on the outputs of this workshop with future stakeholder engagement events and workshops.

1.3 Meeting Set-Up

The meeting was hosted online via Teams with collaborative note-taking via a Google document. Additional resources were provided to participants via Google docs and remained available for editing/contributing one-week post-meeting. The meeting was recorded for note-taking purposes (not to be shared). Chatham house rules (information disclosed during a meeting may be reported by those present, but the source of that information may not be explicitly or implicitly identified) were used to ensure open dialogue. Participants were encouraged to contribute with respect in whichever way comfortable (speaking up, posting in the Teams chat, or writing directly in the notes document).

1.4 Participant Profile

A total of 12 individuals attended the workshop (Figures 1.1, 1.2). The workshop was attended by representatives from NGOs, advisory bodies, managers and responsible authorities, the fishing industry and their representatives, and academia. Participants from Responsible Authority/Management had the greatest representation, forming 33% of the group, followed by those from Advisory Bodies and NGOs (each with 25%), with one member of the fishing industry in attendance and one participant coming from a Research Institute.

Figure 1.1 Participant profile of attendees at the workshop.

Figure 1.2 High Seas Fisheries workshop attendees (for terms see glossary, Appendix 10.2)

2. The OceanICU project

Dr Richard Sanders introduced the OceanICU project. OceanICU is a Pan-European project funded by Horizon Europe and UKRI running from November 2022 to October 2027. It has a consortium of 31 partners across 15 countries. The overall project aim is to produce new data, information and understanding on the role of the ocean in the global carbon cycle. Demands for ocean resources such as food from fish, materials such as trace metals, and blue energy (wind, wave, tidal) are increasing. These increasing demands may affect the uptake of carbon by the ocean due to changes in emissions, industrial processes, and climate change itself. OceanICU recognises the need for knowledge and tools to support decisions makers, managers, and ocean users manage ocean resources, and understand how their interactions with the ocean may affect ocean carbon and hence climate change.

OceanICU is developing new tools that include parameters relevant to management and industry (Figure 2.1). As such, we aim to establish current understanding, perceptions, and needs of stakeholders in relation to oceanic carbon and identify key emerging threats and trajectories. This information will then be used to define scenarios of interest and societal relevance for use in a decision-support tool (DST), and to inform an oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, scenarios, and trade-offs, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services. As part of this, we will produce a multi-sectoral, multi-pressure oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services.

Figure 2.1 Overview of processes considered in the OceanICU project.

3. Outcomes from previous stakeholder engagement activities

Dr Fiona Culhane presented outcomes of previous stakeholder engagement, which consisted of a series of workshops and surveys (Box 3.1) designed to get an understanding of current perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon amongst fishing and deep-sea mining industry communities. Participants included those from fishing and mining industries, management/responsible authorities, advisory bodies, academic/researchers and NGOs (Figure 3.1).

Box 3.1 Summary of previous stakeholder engagement activities

FOUR GROUPS	ONLINE WORKSHOP	SURVEY
High Seas Fishing	✔	✔ "High seas fisheries and ocean carbon – An interactive online workshop" (22 participants)
Shelf Seas Fishing	✔	✔ "Fisheries; socio-economics, ecosystems, and ocean carbon in the Celtic Seas" (21 participants)
Deep Sea Mining	✔	✔ "Deep-sea mining and ocean carbon workshop" (21 participants)
Skipper Expo Fishing		✔ Semi-structured interviews (13 participants)

Figure 3.1 Range of participants from each group involved in workshops, surveys and interviews in 2024. See Box 3.1 for number of participants

A conceptual model of the High Seas-Ocean Carbon social-ecological system, which was co-produced in a previous workshop with High Seas stakeholders, was sense checked since it was produced. This involved running scenarios to visualise changes resulting from increases or decreases in different elements of the model. As part of this sense check, two changes were implemented: The link between seabed impacts and benthic habitats, and the link between species extraction and fish (see Figure 3.2, Insert, red circles), were both changed from a positive arrow to a negative arrow. The rationale for this was that the positive arrows here indicated an increase in seabed impacts species extraction would lead to lead to more habitat or better habitat condition, and similarly, an increase in species extraction would lead to more fish or better fish population condition; thus these arrows should have been negative. The updated model, with this change, was presented during the workshop.

Figure 3.2 Mental model of a high seas fishing-ocean carbon social-ecological system, co-produced with stakeholders using the software MentalModeler. The elements of the model are represented as boxes and colour indicates the type of element: sectors (orange), pressures (blue), ecosystem components (green), ecosystem services (yellow), socio-economic elements (pink). Grey boxes are elements that can be mechanisms of change but are not necessarily pressures. Links between the nodes are represented by lines. Lines are either positive (elements are positively correlated; blue lines), negative (elements have an inverse relationship; red lines), or unknown (thin black lines). Insert: provisional model produced during the first workshop in 2024; Main: Final model after consistency checking and presented to stakeholders in the second workshop in 2025.

The survey/interview questionnaire asked seven ranked questions related to understanding of ocean carbon and interaction with industry (Table 3.1). Participants were asked to rate either how important the statement was or how concerned they were, depending on the question (Figure 3.3). There was overall lower concern for organism loss or damage and impacts on the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP); and for seabed impacts from trawling, dredging or mining; there was low-moderate concern about the carbon footprint of fishing or mining; slightly higher concern about new or emerging marine activities that have links with carbon; and there was moderate-high concern about the water column plume. Participants assigned moderate-high importance to the links between carbon and fishing (or mining) for understanding the BCP and/or climate change and almost all think that the ocean is very important for managing or improving climate change. In terms of differences in group responses, participants coming from eNGOs mostly responded as very concerned/very important across all questions. Managers and advisory bodies had a more moderate response to most questions, and fishing industry had mixed responses with almost all thinking that the ocean is important or very important for helping us to manage climate change, but most were not concerned about impacts of trawling, impacts of removing organisms or the carbon footprint, though there was variability in this. Fishing industry were concerned about other marine activities, and especially Offshore Renewable Energy.

Table 3.1 Questions asked to participants of the workshops and interviews with the abbreviation used in Figure 3.3.

Figure abbreviation	Full question asked
Ocean tackling climate change	How important do you think the ocean is for helping us to manage or improve climate change ?
Carbon-industry links	How important are the links between carbon and fishing/mining for understanding the BCP and/or climate change?
Water column plume	How concerned are you about the fact that disturbing the water column through mining activities can (e.g. water plume effects) can cause disruption to the BCP?
New/growing marine activities	How concerned are you about new or growing activities that are related to carbon and climate change?
Carbon footprint	How concerned are you about the carbon footprint of fishing/mining?
Sea-bed impacts	How concerned are you about the fact that bottom trawling/dredging/mining can cause carbon to be released from sediments?
Organism loss and damage	How concerned are you that removing fish, other animals, plants and algae from the ocean removes ocean carbon/ impacts ?

Figure 3.3 Results from questionnaire and interviews. See Table 3.1 for full question. The ‘water column plume’ question was only asked to participants attending the deep sea mining workshop. Importance or concern goes from 0 - not at all, to 5 - extremely important/concerned.

Finally on the outcomes from previous stakeholder engagements, the results of a thematic analysis were presented (Figure 3.4, Box 3.2). This analysis incorporates some of the key perspectives of the participants who took part in answering the surveys and interviews, as well as those who took part in the discussions during the workshops.

Figure 3.4 Thematic analysis on stakeholder perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon. Note: this work is on-going and the final themes may change.

Box 3.2 Description of themes and subthemes on stakeholder perceptions of ocean carbon. Note: this work is on-going and the final themes may change.

Climate Change

Participants emphasised the need to consider: (1) most climate impacts are coming from land, and therefore ocean based mitigation places an unfair burden on ocean users who may need to change their activities, and (2) any change in ocean activity will have consequences in other ecosystems e.g. less reliance on fish as a low carbon food source would need to be replaced with other protein sources that may have greater impacts on carbon, water and biodiversity.

Care about and valuing the ecosystem

Participants strongly recognised the role of the ocean, biodiversity and habitats in climate regulation, in supplying other ecosystem services and for their intrinsic values. They also expressed concern for ecosystem state for supporting the supply of services and for nature’s sake.

Industry in the wider social-ecological system

Participants spoke about their place in the system in terms of what they provide for society and how they are impacted by factors such as climate change, management and other sectors. Fishing industry stakeholders strongly emphasised that their industry evolves continuously to become more sustainable and mining industry stakeholders also spoke about measures they would take to mitigate impacts. Participants spoke about how their industry is perceived and the evidence underpinning perceptions, which often makes large assumptions, and is then applied across the sector with no differentiation between activity types. A lack of evidence can result in different groups using this to support their own agendas. There were also perceptions about what management might look like and there was a sense of uncertainty and sometimes fear about the future.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant's questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- The presentation was good and a fair synopsis of people's opinion but lacking emphasis on some points. The industry goes to great lengths and efforts to make itself more sustainable and reduce carbon use. Carbon use is directly related to our biggest expense. If you go over 12m, buying carbon is the biggest expense. The less you use, the less expense you have. A lot of technologies are available now. The fleet is old at the moment (36/37 years old average in Europe, the same for Ireland). Even in older vessels, the efficiency is relatively good. Carbon use is reducing, that's the good news, and the work is ongoing, it will evolve and further improve. The reinvestment in the fishing industry is a critical issue. Apart from reducing your use, there are not a lot of options. It's impossible to maintain industry at same level, with no growth, and there is no growth at the moment. Even to maintain the same level of food supply, no option other than carbon use in terms of fuel, and for the most of the fish we eat, there are very little other options than trawling. There's a balance in everything and we need to work to maintain that balance. *That need for balance point is important to make clear.*
- It covered the range of views except to say in terms of decisions about food security and value, it's not just the carbon but also water use, land use, the choices about the ways that we provide to human beings are driven by all sorts of effects. There are wider considerations as well. *That balance between fish as a low carbon food source and the implications for the terrestrial environment if we move away from fish as a main protein source did come out strongly and should be made clear.*

4. Ecosystem and Socio-economic Models

4.1 Oceanic Fisheries and Carbon

Dr Patrick Lehodey presented on development and use of the SEAPODYM model (Lehodey et al., 2008; Senina et al., 2019; 2020) in OceanICU to explore the impact of fishing activities on carbon sequestration and other ecosystem services. Examples of the application of the model to micronekton (Lehodey et al., 2010, 2015; Albernhe et al., 2024) and tuna fisheries were presented. The first part of the study on the carbon footprint of tuna fishing was presented, with the results on the emission by fuel consumption per tonne of landed catch compared to the carbon sequestration linked to the bodies of dead fish that quickly sink to the ocean floor (Mouillot et al., 2023). The carbon flux linked to the excretion by tuna, and that is not remineralized during the descent of this organic carbon to the deep ocean, still needs to be established.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant's questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Does the model consider the horizontal migration of tuna through the Pacific? *Yes, it is the focus of the model. The model is based on advection/diffusion equations to constrain the movement of fish through their feeding habitats, varying according to tuna species and age. The feeding habitat is linked to the modelling of tuna prey (micronekton) that includes surface and mesopelagic groups. For some species it is also possible to introduce shifts between spawning and feeding habitats to create seasonal variations. We estimate movement parameters through fishing data and tagging.*

4.2 Combining environmental sciences and economics to promote sustainable ocean management and conservation policy

Dr Fabio Berzaghi presented on a global study of carbon stored in marine sediments and the market value of this (Berzaghi et al., 2025). Using Mentimeter, he sought feedback on finance of ocean management actions, use of ecosystem services approaches and marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) strategies (Figure 4.2). Dr Gael Mariani then presented on a global model exploring potential conflicts between fishing activity and carbon sequestration (Mariani et al., 2025).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.2 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll on (a) finance of ocean management actions, (b) valuation of ecosystem services and (c) marine Carbon Dioxide Removal strategies.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- The estimates of extraction of nutrients by fisheries in the ocean as a whole from FAO: about 7 and half million tonnes of carbon a year; about 0.2% of the carbon is being taken out by fisheries as a proportion of the total. I think it's interesting you have looked at the spread of the carbon, but in terms of the total, where you say the highest level of fishing and the highest levels of sequestration, what percentage of total carbon is actually removed? It's important for people to understand and make decisions. We need to understand the significance, not just where it is high-high, but does it matter? Also, we don't have much faith in global fish watch at all. We're looking at their figures and see vessels marked as fishing vessels when they're not, and other anomalies. I'd rather you use other types of data in terms of fisheries, such as from FAO. Using this data will result in serious flaws. Great to have the context for decision making, but also whenever you choose to restrict fisheries in one area, it will pop up somewhere else, so must look at the net effect, whether its food production or fishing activity. *For the first question we are trying to publish another paper that estimates the contribution of fish in term of raw numbers and the impact of fishing. This will hopefully come out soon. For the second question, we are aware of the issues related to the use of GFW data, that's why we used two datasets (GFW and Watson et al.) to take into account the issues you raised about GFW. We still included GFW data because it provides some interesting data not considered in other datasets. Moreover, we did the analysis separately using both datasets and the global results are very similar.* About the remarks to close areas to fisheries and the displacement, it is an issue we would have in the future and we should aim to displace fisheries in areas where impact on carbon sequestration can be minimised, hence the need to identify where these fisheries and carbon sequestration areas may or may not be in conflict. I think this would be an interesting contradiction because probably fishing goes where the fish are, to the most productive areas, and the most productive areas are where you have most sequestration. It's always going to be tricky. *If you take the example of high seas compared to coastal areas, in the high seas you don't have a lot of fish biomass compared to coastal areas, but in the high seas you have higher contribution to C sequestration because waters are deep. It can mean that fishing is not ideal here because of the low biomass, but it would have a huge impact on sequestration, so you should displace fishing to coastal areas where biomass is high but where the impacts on carbon sequestration is potentially lower.*
- I agree on the Global Fish Watch data, it's very inconsistent. On the carbon sequestration, if there is increased fishing pressure, that's understood. But if you are working within MSY limits and F ranges, if you're fishing more fish within those ranges, you're fishing from bigger stocks, so your impact on C sequestration would be relative to the size of the fish stock you're fishing. Secondly, if moving fishing from high C sequestration area that is positive but most fishing takes place where sequestration is low and fishing pressure is higher, if we then concentrate that

fishing pressure into a smaller zone due to displacement, does it have a negative or positive effect on carbon sequestration and whole cycle, or if we move from areas with a high volume of fish into an area with less fish and have to increase effort, does it have an impact? Balance in all these things. To be clear we were not able to estimate the impact of fishing on C sequestration, just the potential conflict between fishing and C sequestration. The next objective is to estimate this direct impact. As you said, sometimes fishing might have a positive impact on the overall ocean carbon cycle. For example, removing a top predator might increase mesopelagic fish, which will contribute to BCP. The next steps will be to take into account those trophic relationships to have a global overview of the impact of fishing on all fish, not just commercial species. On the point about displacement, it is something we have to look at to see how accumulating fishing pressure in one area will impact C sequestration.

- Why was a 50 year timeframe was chosen as the C sequestration timeframe, when some mCDR applications are working to 100 years and in the natural system perhaps even longer timeframes (>1000 years) may be more appropriate for permanence sequestration? We decided that 50 is more in line with policy and human perspectives. Of course, the longer the better but when you present management plans that are so far in the future, you don't get a buy in from politicians that are there for 5 or 10 years, so it's more of a compromise. It seems that political decisions are more focused on short term goals. Also, 100 years is more of a legacy, there is no scientific proof that 100 is better than 200. Some recent papers that are showing that even shorter sequestration is beneficial to decrease the warming. But we also have a sensitivity analysis.

5. OceanICU Decision Support Tool

Dr Jorn Bruggeman presented on the Decision Support Tool being developed in the OceanICU project. As part of this, there are several decisions regarding the utility of the tool and what levers the developers should make available for users. Participants gave feedback through Mentimeter polls on questions related to this that will inform the development of the tool (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on how users would want to use the OceanICU Decision Support Tool and the types of levers to include.

Figure 5.1 contd. Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on how users would want to use the OceanICU Decision Support Tool and the types of levers to include.

Figure 5.1 contd. Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on how users would want to use the OceanICU Decision Support Tool and the types of levers to include.

6. Ocean System Pathways: Marine industry development under future scenarios

Dr Natalya Gallo presented on Ocean System Pathways, a framework to explore how marine industries will evolve under different socio-economic pathways and climate change (Maury et al., 2017; 2025; O’Neill et al., 2017). As part of this, participants considered the potential for spatial conflicts with four industries that may grow in the future and provided feedback using Mentimeter polls (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll on spatial conflicts between fishing categories and (a) deep sea mining, (b) offshore wind, (c) dredging, and (d) oil drilling or offshore carbon capture and storage.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant’s questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- The middle of the road scenario. I think it doesn’t do justice for the regional management bodies. It seems quite negative towards the management organizations that already exist. It is not perfect, but they do exist. The sustainability and scientific content are drivers and policies are meant to follow. That drives decisions and industry’s decisions. *Thank you, that’s good feedback.*

7. Wrap up and final words

In the final part of the workshop, participants were asked to reflect on three questions (Table 7.1, Figure 7.1).

Table 7.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll on questions reflecting on ocean carbon

Question	Participant responses
What do you need to know to factor ocean carbon into your work?	Trade-offs between fishing for food security and carbon storage
	Spatial distribution of ocean carbon stocks
	Relationship between healthy fish populations and carbon storage potential
	Remineralisation pathways of ocean carbon from disturbed sediment environments
In what ways can ocean carbon be factored in?	As part of meeting international and national obligations (Global Biodiversity Framework commitments/actions, net zero, etc.)

Figure 7.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant's questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Some of the areas are developing quickly like mCDR and geoengineering, what conflicts might arise from these technologies? I attended a workshop last week about marine carbon dioxide removal technologies and interactions with fisheries, but there is movement around that. In this working group we'll try to explore those issues; hopefully there'll be more about that in the future, it is a quickly developing space.

Action points following the meeting:

- Summary report to be written and circulated for review and feedback. Key messages will be communicated through this report and in other relevant fora.
- Ensure points raised by participants in feedback on the thematic analysis are incorporated in future presentation/reports of this work.
- The results from the questions around the Decision Support Tool (DST) will be reviewed and combined with outputs from the shelf seas and deep-sea mining groups. Researchers will look to incorporate participant preferences in subsequent iterations of the DST.
- For OceanICU, additional follow-up workshops will be arranged with shelf seas, high seas and deep-sea mining stakeholders.

8. Conclusions

Active engagement from the invited participants led to a successful outcome for the workshop with valuable information on relevant management/policy questions and information to help the development of realistic future scenarios to progress towards applied tool development and ensure OceanICU outputs meet stakeholder and end-user needs. Outcomes included:

- Participants stated that to maintain our current supply of food from fish, reinvestment in the fishing industry is required if we also want to reduce the carbon footprint of fisheries (including those resulting from the disturbance of the sediment via bottom trawling). The fishing industry is working towards sustainability but does not have other options to both reduce emissions and maintain food supply.
- Participants feel it is important for decision makers need to understand the wider context, trade-offs and the consequences of decisions, which are potentially complex and currently unclear. For example,
 - What is the significance of fisheries impacts in terms of total ocean carbon?
 - Any reduction in food supply coming from fish may have wider implications for carbon but also water use, land use, and other environmental impacts (e.g. if consumers switch to land-based proteins such as beef and pork).

- Displacement of fisheries from areas of high carbon sequestration may have wider impacts if e.g. fish stocks are lower in displaced areas.
- Identification of participant preferences for how to configure the DST.
- Development of future scenarios should consider the current management already in operation.

The above points will guide the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU. They will help form the basis of scenarios to test using a range of modelling approaches, help to develop the DST, and help to develop future scenarios for ocean system pathways. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the participants and wider stakeholder group.

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10. Appendices

10.1 Agenda

Time (GMT)	Program
09.00 – 09.20	Introduction to workshop, housekeeping, and OceanICU project
09.20 – 10.15	Follow up on previous workshop outcomes
10.15 – 10.45	SEAPODYM: Spatial ecosystem and population dynamics model
10.45 – 11.05	Global economic and environmental models
11.05 – 11.20	Break
11.20 – 12.20	Decision Support Tools in OceanICU
12.20 – 12.50	Future Scenarios: Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
12.50 – 13.00	Wrap up and final words

10.2 Acronyms

- BCP: Biological Carbon Pump
- CO₂: Carbon dioxide
- DST: Decision Support Tool
- IEO-CSIC: Instituto Español de Oceanografía - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spanish National Research Council)
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- ISE FPO: Irish South and East Fish Producers Organisation
- mCDR: marine Carbon Dioxide Removal
- NEAFC: North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission
- (e)NGO: (environmental) non-governmental organisation
- OceanICU: Improving Carbon Understanding
- RMFO: Regional Fisheries Management Organisation

10.3 Participant List

List of participants (blue shading indicates OceanICU/workshop organisers)

Name	Organisation
	Aquatic Life Institute
	North East-Atlantic Fisheries Commission
	ISEFPO (Irish South & East Fish Producers Organisation)
	Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries
	COV-IEO (CSIC)
	Intl. Seafood Sustainability Foundation
	National Institute of Water & Atmospheric Research (NIWA)
	Oceans North
	European Commission
	IEO-CSIC
	Geological Survey of Norway
	European Commission
Fabio Berzaghi	WMU
Fiona Culhane	Marine Institute
Gael Mariani	WMU
Jorn Bruggeman	Bolding & Bruggeman ApS
Maylis Sontot-Marjary	Marine Institute
Natalya Gallo	Norce
Patrick Lehodey	Mercator
Richard Sanders	Norce
Thibault Cariou	Marine Institute
Karsten Bolding	Bolding & Bruggeman ApS

10.4 Resources

- Albernhe S., Gorgues T., Titaud O., Lehodey P., Menkes C, Conchon A. (2025). Micronekton indicators evolution based on biophysically defined provinces. State of The Planet. <https://doi.org/10.5194/sp-2024-35>
- ICES workshop on Assessing the Impact of Fishing on Oceanic Carbon (WKFISHCARBON; outputs from 2023 meeting): https://ices-library.figshare.com/articles/report/Workshop_on_Assessing_the_Impact_of_Fishing_on_Oceanic_Carbon_WKFISHCARBON_outputs_from_2023_meeting_/24949122
- OceanICU Decision Support Tool prototype: <https://ocean-icu.lab.dive.edito.eu/>
- OceanICU webinars (including Fish, Fisheries and Carbon webinar): <https://ocean-icu.eu/webinars/>
- OceanICU: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>
- SEAPODYM Codebase available at: <https://github.com/PacificCommunity/seapodym-codebase>
- Stakeholder Mailing List Sign Up for OceanICU <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUjoin>